

Implementation of Church Social Teachings (Asg) in School Learning

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ABSTRACT: This writing aims to provide inspiration for teachers in developing learning in schools, especially in Civics lessons. Civics learning in the classroom which is considered boring for students becomes a fun learning in the classroom by recognizing students' learning needs. Learning that provides a large space for students to grow and develop according to their potential and talents by paying attention to the learning needs of each student. Classroom learning that emphasizes reasoning activities, good feelings and wills so that fun learning is created in the classroom. This writing is a process of feeling and reasoning of teachers in the classroom by looking at the existing reality, to be reflected in depth so as to produce learning that is preferred by students and becomes an idol at school. Development of learning based on humanitarian values and church social values that are developed in depth into character education in schools. This writing is an inspiration for teachers in developing meaningful learning. Through observation and processing of experiences that are used as writing data that is reconstructed into a written work. Data collection carried out in the classroom and data processing carried out in a deep reflective manner makes this writing more meaningful and profound. The focus of this writing is to help teachers in the classroom in changing the paradigm in providing teaching based on the potential and learning needs of students in the classroom and realizing civics learning that students like so that learning is more enjoyable. Critical reflection and deep analysis of the author's data and experiences as a basis for presenting a reconstruction of events that are easily captured and interpreted by readers. With this writing, it is hoped that it can help schools to build a paradigm in presenting inspiring and moving civics learning so that positive cultures are born in the classroom. Hopefully this writing can provide color to the world of education and positive inspiration to continue to explore more creative and innovative strengths and potentials.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Education always adheres to the principles of norms and morals that make society feel confident that with education humans are worthy and worthy to do good in order to save others. Based on the opinion above, it means that education will make humans more dignified in life. It should be remembered that the basis for making humans more moral lies in the process of forming the personality of each individual. Here the role of education as a builder of the mentality of the younger generation is very important.

Based on the opinion of Prof. Dr. Driyarkara, S.J., education is the process of forming young humans so that they have a complete and attractive personality. Because a complete and integrated personality is multidimensional, the right education is a comprehensive education that pays attention to various aspects of personality in a balanced manner (see in Al. Hadiwardoyo, M.S.F.,: Moral education in higher education, Pelangi Pendidikan, A.M. Slamet Soewandi, D.K.K (Editor), USD Publisher, Yogyakarta, 2005., p., 92). This clearly indicates that students are not understood only as objects in education but as subjects who have a total comprehensive dimension as perfect human beings created by God.

For this reason, an understanding is needed from educators that exploitation of students that leads to coercion, intimidation or the restraint of ideas must be ended immediately. The approach used must also be multicultural and multidimensional. The treatment of students as unique and interesting individuals is also a special concern and must be understood by all components of educators.

The main goal of education is to produce positive changes in students so that they are able to grow and develop into effective individuals and citizens. (A. Supratiknya: The Current Indonesian Education System in Psychological Perspective, *ibid.*,

p. 179). By considering this reality, education is very important in order to develop more complex student abilities and have better life skills. Students must be able to show who they really are leading to self-maturity.

Adolescence is a special concern for parents and teachers at school. It should be remembered that at this time teenagers will feel that they want to be free to do something according to their own will and their peers. The concept of right will be seen from the extent to which the action is exciting for them and accepted in society. At this time, it is not uncommon for teenagers to violate norms or ethics that have long been formed and sometimes they do not want to accept suggestions and input from teachers or parents.

Actually, this is where the role of educator's lies in helping students find their identity which sometimes begins to be "lost" by the flow of fashion or lifestyle. At this time students are given the opportunity to learn to distinguish between good and bad, so that in the future they will gradually no longer need regulations from their parents because they can determine what is best for themselves. (Anita Lie: 101 Ways to Grow Children's Intelligence, Elex Media Komputindo, Jakarta, 2004). This means that students are trained and prepared to determine their own life path from an early age so that they do not always depend on their parents or family environment. This is done with full awareness to help the process of student discovery and awareness, not with threats, insults or intimidation wrapped in the words "must" and or "must". Every teenager certainly also wants to find their identity with the help of those around them including teachers so that they can find a self-concept that will lead them to success. Self-concept will make a person more attractive and successful. To understand the existence of a good self-concept, a person needs to reset or reprogram his mental computer so that he will know how to use or create a self-concept that will be used in guiding or managing himself (cf., Adi W. Gunawan: Born to be a Genius, PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta, 2003., p. 4). In this case, schools must dare to facilitate all forms of student activities in order to find or discover themselves as perfect beings. Students will feel proud and happy if it turns out that they are dignified and unique human beings and are part of God's plan.

For this reason, guidance from educators is needed so that in discovering their identity, students do not feel patronized, full of coercion. They need a good role model that can be accepted from a teenager's perspective, exciting and appreciative of a person. They need control over norms and ethics that come from a "friend" figure or someone who wants to understand their current situation.

The above phenomenon makes something interesting to discuss further, this is because schools are agents of change for the younger generation in order to realize a better quality of the next generation. In addition, as a means to change the paradigm of thinking that is more comprehensive about civics learning for both educators (teachers) and students themselves.

1.2. Problem formulation

Education is an agent of change for the younger generation to become more qualified so that in this global era they can compete with the outside world. To realize this ideal, the role of educators is very central in striving for human resources of international standard. However, at the level of implementation in the field, educators sometimes do not understand the characteristics of today's young generation so that philosophically it will interfere with the development process itself. In civics learning, for example, the paradigm of society, especially the teachers themselves, is less able to understand the essence of civics lessons which are actually full of moral education, values, problem solving and give rise to new conclusions.

To discuss further, this article formulates several questions, including:

1. How to build a new paradigm in civics learning?
2. How to make civics learning interesting for students?

CHAPTER II

PROBLEM ANALYSIS

2.1. New paradigm in civics learning

Today, the world of education is increasingly depressed because it is considered to have failed to educate the young generation of Indonesia. And the biggest portion of failure is the teaching model that has been applied so far. It is undeniable that for decades education has only presented memorization and students are considered as photocopiers who have to memorize pages and pages. Students are not invited to think and how to think to develop their lives. Education does not touch on the formation of a person's character and morality so that what emerges is dehumanization and moral decadence. Apart from the factors that cause failure, teachers play an important role in the success or failure of the learning process.

If we look back for a moment with the learning process so far, the world of education (teachers, ed.) still uses the old paradigm so that students are not given the free opportunity to actively create their ideas or thoughts. In other words, students are empty bottles that must be filled as much as possible, this implies that students must be willing to give up their rights when being filled. The command and omniscient system becomes a very powerful mantra to always legitimize their actions.

In the old paradigm, it is undeniable that teachers often do the following things, for example; transferring knowledge from teacher to student, categorizing students based on their level of success in memorizing and encouraging students to compete like fighting cocks. (see; Anita Lie: Cooperative Learning, Grasindo, Jakarta, 2003, p. 3). Along with the demands of the times and the increasing need for education, the world of education must improve itself so that better quality education is created. For that, teachers must dare to change the old paradigm into a newer paradigm. Teachers should not only brandish a bent, rusty and blunt keris in the

learning process. Now heirlooms are not only keris but there are many more that have the same function and are even more efficient in their use.

In learning Civics, educators need to create a learning construction that is contained in a syllabus or RPP (learning implementation plan) that is neatly structured so that it is easily understood at the practical level. The syllabus and lesson plans after being signed by the principal should not only be kept in a museum and worshiped. Therefore, the construction of learning must include the following: first; the knowledge created is discovered, formed and developed by students. Second, students are given the freedom to actively build knowledge, third; teachers need to develop their competence and students' abilities through discovery activities. Fourth; the establishment of good interactions and relationships between students and educators. (ibidem., p. 5).

At the junior high school level, civics lessons are known as lessons on the sudra caste or even pariahs. This is because students are reluctant to follow boring lessons, memorization, and teachers who are sometimes annoying. Hearing the word civics, some children are allergic and nauseous, just because of obligations and fear of bad grades, students are forced to follow with a high level of coercion. Even at the high school level, certain schools do not include exam schedules either at the end of the semester or mid-semester for civics lessons. This shows that the school does not provide the right portion for students to develop their character and national participation. The wrong teaching and approaches practiced by teachers in class during teaching contribute the most to this decline. It is undeniable that the decline occurred because of the national education system, curriculum development and politicization in the world of education.

Civics learning is actually full of values that contribute to a person's success in society. Just imagine someone's success in business, diplomacy, regional or international relations cannot be separated from social interaction. In this interaction, a person is required to be able to understand character, social ethics and spirituality so that a person succeeds in exploring attitudes, desires and building agreements with others. The approach used is a social approach, not a mathematical or natural law approach. So that Civics learning in schools is not boring and has a place in the hearts of students, teachers must avoid memorization methods and the "pokoke" or absolute law approach. Civics learning must prioritize accurate, up-to-date information, understanding and appreciation of science, life values and morals clearly.

To operationalize these objectives, teachers should pay attention to the following (cf.; Sutarjo Adi Susilo: Value education methods in the humanities; paper presented in the Alumni Seminar of the Department of Social Science Education, Sanata Dharma University, Yogyakarta, 2000): First, learning must be student-centric, namely teachers must understand the condition of students, pay attention to their development and there must be maximum evaluation related to the picture of student development. Second; learning must be humanistic, namely students must be understood and appreciated as whole human beings with a family atmosphere in the classroom. With this approach, students will easily explore their talents and interests. Third; using a multidimensional or multi-truth learning approach, multi-media and multi-evaluation. This means that students will enjoy learning more and create joyful learning, students at home in class, and easily understand the material and mistakes made so that they are easy to fix. Multi-media makes it easy for students to compare and study from various learning sources. Fourth; active and creative participation of students in the classroom. Teachers must succeed in involving students in the learning process so that students will have a sense of belonging in every activity. The learning process is made as interesting as possible by conveying the conceptual framework clearly and highlighting the values contained in the facts. Teachers must dare to bring up values that can be raised and internalized to become a joint movement, for example, raising the values of justice and democratization.

The values that have been found are practiced and internalized in their daily lives and it would be better for teachers to work together with parents/guardians of students to monitor their implementation. It is easy as follows: students are given the task of making a daily report of the values that have been applied daily at home, parents sign the report assignment and the teacher checks the extent of its implementation through the book. In class, the teacher invites students to reflect on these values, their benefits and what obstacles are found in their implementation. In learning Civics learn, teachers can also use a social science approach, for example; Value Clarification Technique (VCT). This approach includes, among others: first: Evocation Approach (evocation approach): Students are given the freedom to express their feelings, assessments and responses to learning objects, the freedom to raise the values contained in the learning process. Second: directed suggestion approach, namely the teacher must create a stimulant for students and subtly direct them to a directed conclusion. Third: awareness approach: in this approach, students are invited to observe the surrounding environment to be aware of their existence, others and the environment. Fourth: Moral Reasoning (finding moral values), namely the facilitator creates a dilemma to be solved together and participants are expected to find the moral values contained therein. (cf., ibidem., p. 3). Students are also invited to reflect on the extent to which these values build their mentality. In this approach, the form of activity can be in the form of discussion, case studies, watching films and so on. Example: in Civics learning at Santa Maria junior high school in Surabaya, the teacher (author, ed.,) plays a film about human rights violations, the indicator to be achieved is that students are able to analyze cases of human rights violations that occurred in Indonesia, then after finishing playing the film, the class is divided into several working groups and each finds the values contained in the film. The activity was closed by reflecting (for 10 minutes) on the benefits of these values for daily life so that it is hoped that students have a stock of humanist values and this will be useful when they later enter society.

In order to implement the above approaches, teachers must be skilled in controlling the class. Teachers must be able to map the class so that activities can run smoothly without having to be "intimidated" in the classroom. In addition, in their learning techniques, teachers should create varied questions so that an atmosphere of freedom will be created for students to determine the answers without having to be boxed in by the answers that have been made by their teachers. The forms of questions include (see and cf. Ibidem., page 7):

- a. Exploratory questions, namely to find out how far students understand the material, for example: after watching the show or event, are there any of you who feel sad? Why!, and others.
- b. Clarification questions, namely to find out the depth of students' understanding of a material, for example: Explain the meaning or essence of the human rights violation cases that you have studied!
- c. Questions to ask for reasons, for example; In the incident, there were people who were ganged up on by the masses. Was the ganging up a good action? Why is that? Explain!
- d. Guided questions are to help students find useful life values, for example; From a number of your friends' answers, it was stated that human rights violations cannot be justified by anyone or anything. Do the moral teachings of the nation, religion and law also think so? Give a comment!
- e. Questions that are personification or analogy. This question helps students to be sharper in analyzing and finding a better attitude or life values. This really helps students to realize the meaning of the nature of humans and society. The question, for example; For example, Andi answered that the beatings in the film were okay as a lesson for the demonstrators. Now try to imagine that the demonstrators were your older or younger siblings? Would you still act like that?

With the variation of these questions, students can explore and teachers can complete the curriculum load that is indeed their responsibility. Students will enjoy taking social lessons. Emotional bonds between each other and interactions will be well established along with fun and non-boring learning activities. Philosophically, it can be formulated that in learning, students are happy and can interpret what they are learning. The existence of appreciation for the entire class community, mutual respect and appreciation between class components, helping each other will be provisions in the future so that a good national civilization will be created through the younger generation. This is actually an answer to the need for education so far, especially for the subject of Civics which is felt to be very annoying and boring.

Indonesian education which is currently just improving and is far from the orientation of education which should really create humane people. Current education is experiencing shallowing of humanity, society is easily divided, anarchic actions are everywhere, and not respecting each other seems to be the characteristic of this nation. (see ., Gerrbang Magazine; in the figure of Ahmad Syafii Maarif; The small boat saved by the waves., Muhammadiyah University of Yogyakarta., 4th edition V-2005). With the instillation of life values that are integrated into the teaching and learning process, it is hoped that education will save humans, not erode the values of humanity itself. Education will make a great nation that is full of good attitudes to living in society, politeness, humanity and friendliness will create a strong and dignified country.

2.2. Civics learning "idol" for students

Freedom here is not interpreted as being completely free but freedom that can respect the freedom of others as social beings. Freedom that is more directed as a way of thinking and acting based on the nature of human beings who are rational. In addition to ethical freedom of expression, each individual is also expected to be able to use freedom of reasoning according to their own abilities or thinking power so that they will find a self-concept that can be used as a reference for taking every action without being swayed by circumstances.

In the process of learning Civics, it is always attempted to see that students as free and autonomous human beings, so an approach and understanding of the general conditions of the class are needed. Educators will always explore students' abilities that are adjusted to the basic competencies that will be taken in each content standard. Determination and selection of indicators in learning are absolute things that need special attention so that students are able and willing to open themselves up and explore their abilities.

Students' freedom to express and express their opinions needs to be supported by the methods that will be used in learning. The choice of learning method is the key where students are willing to be invited to find the essence of the knowledge itself together. The teacher's motivation for students will also affect the way and what the students want to do after that. Students will certainly be motivated if they feel challenged to gain the knowledge. Throughout the author's experience, students will feel proud if in their learning method they are given the freedom to express themselves or visualize themselves in the form of actions. For that, it is necessary to create a mapping of basic competencies or indicators that will use certain methods. For example, in learning Civics learn for grade 7 on the basic competency of community participation in regional autonomy or describing cases of human rights violations, the method used is a portfolio. In this method, the class is divided into several groups to discuss the "Lapindo Mud Disaster in Sidoarjo". Each group discusses from a different perspective, for example: group A analyzes that the Lapindo Mud Disaster could be a human rights violation, group B looks for efforts that have been taken by the government and assesses whether they are successful or not, group C determines the government's strategic policies in dealing with the case and group D creates a mapping of problems regarding handling mud victims by offering the concept of environmentally friendly development. Group D

is tasked with convincing the mudflow victims that they are willing to move voluntarily by offering a healthy, clean, cheap and environmentally friendly settlement. The group will create an independent city area by considering certain aspects. They can realize it in a housing model and location map.

With this method, students will be free to visualize themselves and freely express their opinions without any pressure or fear of being blamed. This will train their thinking skills without having to follow the thinking framework or thinking concept of their teacher. Students will be accustomed to making mind maps that stem from their ability to explore all the facilities and abilities they have. The mind map will help in mastering each basic competency that will be taken. In the mind map, students will be able to draw basic concepts and information obtained by emphasizing the main ideas that emerge. This will help students remember or draw a conclusion about a case without having to cram their brains with one-way information. By using color and three-dimensional maps, students will be more confident in making basic concepts in their mind maps. Creative students will use their thinking skills to freely express their ideas or thoughts and thus the Lapindo mud disaster problem in Sidoarjo can be resolved according to the students' way of thinking.

With the ability to imagine, this knowledge will be firmly embedded in the child's mind map, this is possible because every idea that arises and is left wide open so that the thinking map will develop organically and increase rather than being suppressed. (cf., Tony Buzan: *Using Your Head, thinking techniques, learning and building the brain.*, without publisher and year, p. 127). In addition to using the portfolio method, there are many more that can be used to explore students' thinking abilities, for example observation with the help of VCDs by selecting documentary films that are in accordance with the indicators or basic competencies that will be taken. Using snakes and ladders or monopoly games by entering concept material in each box in the game. Students also have the right to determine the punishment and points for each group that violates the game. In this method, students must be sporty and aware that every step has its rules. The meaning that can be taken from this method is that students are aware that in this life there are always rules, the impact of violating the rules and the willingness to obey every rule.

With this learning pattern, it is hoped that the material will be easily achieved, students feel happy in using their thinking skills without being intimidated by the rules or systems that apply. They feel free to express their opinions, act and they are also aware that wrong attitudes and ways of thinking will impact or harm others. They feel like they are free people in their class and most importantly are able to grasp the material without having to be tortured. With a learning process that emphasizes proactive student learning methods, students will experience more comprehensive development and self-maturation. It is hoped that students can manage themselves in the sense that they know when to act, with whom and how the action can be carried out. In decision making, students can explore their reasoning abilities, their imagination so that everything is conceptualized in their mind map so that a critical, creative, imaginative and innovative attitude emerges.

Civics learning can produce students who excel in all things, not only intellectually but also grow emotional and spiritual intelligence. In their daily practice, educators are expected to be able to foster student awareness at a more behavioral level in the sense that individual awareness is not built on intimidation or terror but rather prioritizes togetherness and personal respect as dignified and noble beings.

Empirical reflection is one effort to raise students' awareness as moral and ethical human beings. As a formal education that emphasizes the intellectual aspect, Civics learning tries to produce students who have life skills. The life skills that are to be highlighted lie in two aspects, namely employ ability skills and vocational skills. Employ ability skills include several skills including basic skills, high-level thinking, character building and affective skills.

In this case, Civics learning invites students to diligently seek out every actual information through reading news in newspapers or library magazines, the internet and so on. The information obtained by students is then processed together with their work groups, then students learn to make case mapping. Students conduct a review of information by finding the essence of the case, the cause of its occurrence and its solution. Problem solving in every learning activity stimulates students to be able to develop their reasoning and imagination so that they can make quick and accurate decisions.

At the behavioral level, students can carry out or display the results of their thoughts in everyday life without having to hesitate or be embarrassed by paying attention to the principle of humanity. The vocational skill aspect includes special skills to do special jobs. In this case, idealistic civics learning expects students to be able to design or create certain concepts in the case study activities they carry out. These concepts are in the form of crystallization of new ideas from several competent students. This activity is seen in the learning of grade 7 students when several students who are appointed and categorized as capable of making problem mapping and new city area models as an effort to solve the Lapindo mud problem in Sidoarjo. Problem mapping is based on the real conditions of the community and the capabilities of the government. In mapping the problems, students also propose designs for healthy and environmentally friendly residential areas. By raising the theme of environmentally friendly Porong Baru city development, students can imagine with natural maps, regional images, building shapes or building models as well as visualize all their thoughts.

CHAPTER III CLOSING

Basically, freedom of thought can help students find their identity as dignified human beings. Therefore, in the learning process, students are expected to be open to all forms of constructive input, as are their educators. Students and educators must work together on the same mission, namely to create a young generation that is intellectually, emotionally and spiritually intelligent. Leadership or leadership spirit also grows along with intellectual development. It is expected that after completing education, each individual will be able to manage themselves, be moral and have a high humanitarian attitude towards increasingly solid maturity without abandoning increasingly developing religious values. Teachers as educators must be able to change the paradigm in Civics learn learning. Students must receive guidance in finding their identity and freedom in developing themselves. A multidimensional approach is the right solution amidst the storm of the Civics learn learning crisis in society.

The numerical approach that has been practiced by many teachers does not need to be used as an absolute reference in determining student success in learning, especially Civics learn learning. Teachers must dare to break the old paradigm that makes teachers the command or head of troops. Teachers do not create a generation of "sarimin-sarimin" who are obedient, obedient and follow all the wishes of those who rule. It should be understood that teachers educate a young generation that is dignified, unique and has a myriad of potentials that may not have been revealed or cannot reveal these potentials. For that, the social sciences approach must be truly applied so that students as the young generation can build good character or personality, have good intellect and are able to develop their potentials.

In order to make Civics learning interesting, in addition to changing the paradigm, teachers should be able to innovate in Civics learning. The PAIKEM technique and method which has been a "superior product" must be truly implemented properly. The method applied is actually adjusted to the characteristics of each school and the most important thing is the supporting facilities, human resources. A good method does not lie in a certain dogma or law but that the method can be used and enjoyed by all components in learning so that the substance of education is truly achieved properly.

With the change in the new paradigm and qualified learning management, Civics learning will certainly become an "idol" in schools. Civics learning which is actually full of human values, comprehensive conceptual understanding and good problem-solving framework can be used as an effort to improve the quality of education in Indonesia. In the midst of the onslaught of dehumanizing and demoralizing education, Civics learning is present in the midst of society which offers various alternative solutions that are very relevant to the current development of the era. Philosophically, the main purpose of education to humanize humans and education that saves can be answered with the presence of new nuances in Civics learning.

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